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Enterprises Operating in the Arts, Entertainment, and Recreation Sector in OECD Countries

The OECD calculates the number of enterprises operating in the arts, entertainment, and recreation sector. This category includes creative, artistic, and entertainment activities; libraries, archives, museums, and other cultural activities; gambling and betting activities; and sports and recreational activities. The data refers to the period between 2021 and 2022.

Enterprises Operating in the Arts, Entertainment, and Recreation Sector in OECD Countries in 2022. France emerges as the undisputed leader with 137,941 enterprises in the arts, entertainment, and recreation sector. This figure is not surprising, given that France is historically known for its strong support for the arts and culture, with a vast artistic heritage and very active cultural policies. French public policies, which include grants and incentives for cultural industries, have likely contributed to this high number of enterprises. The Netherlands follows closely with 123,659 enterprises. This number reflects the importance of the creative sector in the Dutch economy, which is known for being an international hub for design, fashion, and digital arts. A focus on innovation and creative industries is a distinctive feature of the Dutch economic model. Spain, with 105,757 enterprises, ranks third. Spain has a rich cultural tradition and a vibrant art scene, including festivals, museums, and a strong film industry. Here too, cultural tourism plays a significant role, supporting many of the enterprises in the arts and entertainment sector. Germany, with 85,537 enterprises, and Italy, with 74,505, follow in the ranking. Both countries have an exceptional cultural heritage and a strong creative sector. In Germany, cities like Berlin are recognized as centers of cultural and artistic innovation, while in Italy the historical and artistic heritage continues to support a large number of enterprises in the sector. Sweden, with 54,174 enterprises, and Portugal, with 44,308, show significant numbers, although lower than the previous countries. Sweden is known for its pop music and a vibrant digital entertainment sector, while Portugal is rapidly growing as a cultural and creative destination, with Lisbon emerging as one of the new cultural centers in Europe. Norway, with 36,047 enterprises, and Hungary, with 32,204, represent the next block. Norway has a strong music and visual arts sector, while Hungary has a long tradition in cinema and performing arts. Further down the ranking, we find countries like Turkey (29,558), Poland (29,275), and the Czech Republic (27,886). These countries are rapidly developing their creative sectors, with increasing investments in the arts and entertainment, supported by government policies and growing domestic and international interest. Israel, with 25,891 enterprises, and Belgium, with 25,185, reflect the importance of the creative sector in their economies. Israel is known for its technological innovation, which is also reflected in the digital arts sector, while Belgium has a long tradition of comics, design, and visual arts. Other countries like Greece (19,360), Finland (18,882), and Lithuania (13,105) show more modest but still significant numbers. Greece is trying to revive its cultural sector, while Finland is known for its design and architecture. Lithuania, smaller in size, is developing its creative sector with a focus on new technologies and contemporary art. The numbers continue to decrease for countries like Slovenia (9,057), the Slovak Republic (8,379), and Costa Rica (7,510). These countries, although smaller, are

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making notable progress in the arts and entertainment sector, with local initiatives aimed at enhancing cultural heritage and promoting creativity. Countries like Denmark (6,870), Latvia (6,164), and Estonia (5,222) also have relatively low numbers but show a growing commitment to creative industries. Denmark has a strong music and design scene, while Latvia and Estonia are emerging as new cultural destinations in Europe. Towards the bottom of the ranking, we find Bulgaria (5,171), Switzerland (4,108), Croatia (3,723), Cyprus (2,396), Malta (2,214), and Serbia (2,080). These countries have smaller economies and a developing arts and entertainment sector. However, each of them has its cultural and creative niches that are beginning to flourish. At the end of the list are North Macedonia (774), Luxembourg (698), and Bosnia and Herzegovina (507). These very low numbers reflect smaller economies and perhaps fewer resources allocated to creative industries, but even here there are signs of growth and development in the sector.

Changes between 2021 and 2022. Austria, for example, saw a significant reduction of 3,453 enterprises, equal to a negative percentage change of 11.62%. This decline could be attributed to various factors, including a possible reduction in public funding for the arts or a drop in demand for entertainment services due to pandemic-related restrictions. The temporary closure of theaters, museums, galleries, and other cultural venues likely had a negative impact on the sector, leading many enterprises to close or suspend activities. In contrast, Belgium saw an increase of 1,919 enterprises, corresponding to an 8.25% rise. This increase may reflect renewed interest in recreational and cultural activities, potentially stimulated by favorable government policies or an economic recovery post-pandemic that encouraged investments in the sector. Belgium, with its rich tradition of cultural events, festivals, and strong support for the arts, seems to have benefited from a favorable environment for the growth of creative enterprises. Costa Rica, on the other hand, experienced a decrease of 563 enterprises, corresponding to a 6.97% drop. This decline could be linked to local economic factors or a shift in household spending priorities, with fewer resources allocated to recreational activities. The decrease in international tourism during the pandemic may have negatively impacted many enterprises in the entertainment and recreation sector. The Czech Republic registered an increase of 1,807 enterprises, equal to a 6.93% rise, signaling stable growth in the sector. This increase could be the result of government incentives or an expanding cultural industry attracting new enterprises. The vibrant art scene in Prague and other Czech cities may have contributed to this growth. Denmark saw a modest increase of 309 enterprises, with a 4.71% variation. This increase may indicate slow but steady growth in the sector, possibly supported by good management of the country's cultural and recreational resources. Denmark is known for its design, music, and cinema, which may have supported the growth of enterprises in these sectors. Estonia experienced an impressive growth of 19.99%, with an increase of 870 enterprises. This significant increase suggests a rapidly expanding sector, likely fueled by technological innovation and a vibrant local art scene. Estonia is known for its advanced digital environment, which may have facilitated the growth of enterprises in the digital arts and online entertainment sector. In Finland, the number of enterprises increased by 1,532, with an 8.83% rise. Finland is renowned for its design and architecture, and this growth may reflect an increase in demand for creative products and services. Helsinki, in particular, is a vibrant center for design and the arts, which may have contributed to this increase. France saw a significant reduction of 9,883 enterprises, corresponding to a 6.69% decline. This decrease could be due to various factors, including changes in cultural policies, a reduction in public funding, or the effects of the pandemic on cultural and recreational activities. The closure of many cultural venues during the pandemic may have had a lasting impact on the sector. Germany saw an increase of 5,528 enterprises, with a 6.91% rise. This increase can be attributed to a robust economic recovery and strong support for the creative industries, which are a fundamental part of the German economy. Berlin, with its renowned art and cultural scene, may have played a key role in this growth. In Greece, there was an increase of 1,182 enterprises, with a 6.50% rise. This increase may be the result of renewed interest in cultural tourism and the arts, sectors that are vital to the Greek economy. Greece, with its rich historical and cultural heritage, continues to be an attractive destination for investments

in the arts and entertainment sector. Hungary registered a growth of 1,835 enterprises, corresponding to a 6.04% rise. This figure suggests an expansion of the creative sector, perhaps stimulated by government incentives or an increase in demand for recreational activities. Budapest, with its vibrant cultural scene, may have contributed to this growth. Israel saw an increase of 2,178 enterprises, with a 9.18% rise. This increase may be indicative of strong development in the creative industries, supported by technological innovations and a vibrant cultural scene. Tel Aviv, in particular, is a center of innovation and creativity that may have favored the growth of enterprises in the sector. Italy registered a modest increase of 1,027 enterprises, corresponding to a 1.40% rise. This slight increase may reflect stability in the sector, with a balance between new enterprises and those that closed. Italy, with its vast cultural and artistic heritage, continues to support a significant number of enterprises in the arts and entertainment sector. Latvia saw an impressive growth of 22.23%, with an increase of 1,121 enterprises. This figure suggests significant expansion in the sector, possibly linked to favorable policies or an increase in interest in the arts and entertainment. Riga, the capital, may be a center of this growth. Lithuania registered an increase of 1,517 enterprises, with a 13.09% rise. This increase may reflect an expanding art scene and strong support for the creative industries. Vilnius, the capital, is known for its vibrant cultural scene. Luxembourg saw a slight decrease of 68 companies, equivalent to 8.88%. This decline could be attributed to local economic factors or a reduction in demand for recreational services. Being a small country, even modest changes can have a significant impact on the percentages. The Netherlands recorded an increase of 4,858 businesses, or 4.09%. This increase reflects stable growth in the sector, supported by favorable policies and strong demand for cultural activities. Amsterdam, with its arts and culture scene, could be a driver of this growth. Norway saw an increase of 4,954 businesses, a growth of 15.93%. This data indicates a strong expansion of the sector, perhaps stimulated by a high demand for recreational and cultural activities. Norway, with its strong musical and artistic tradition, continues to be an attractive location for businesses in the sector. Poland suffered a slight decrease of 1,019 companies, equal to 3.36%. This decline could reflect changes in consumer preferences or a reduction in funding for the arts. However, Poland continues to be an emerging cultural center in Europe. Portugal recorded a significant increase of 5,700 businesses, with growth of 14.76%. This increase may be the result of favorable policies and a strong interest in cultural tourism. Lisbon, in particular, has emerged as a new cultural center in Europe. Slovakia saw an increase of 544 companies, equal to 6.94%. This increase reflects stable growth in the sector, supported by an increase in demand for recreational activities. Bratislava could be a center of this growth. Slovenia recorded an increase of 448 companies, with a growth of 5.20%. This data indicates modest but constant growth in the sector. Ljubljana, the capital, is known for its vibrant cultural scene. Spain saw an increase of 1,529 companies, equal to 1.47%. This slight increase reflects stability in the sector, with a balance between new businesses and those that have closed. Spain, with its rich cultural heritage, continues to support a significant number of businesses in the arts and entertainment sector. Sweden suffered a significant reduction of 7,203 businesses, or 11.74%. This decline could be attributed to various factors, including changes in cultural policies or a reduction in demand for recreational services. The pandemic may have had a negative impact on many businesses in the sector. Switzerland saw a slight decrease of 271 companies, equal to 6.19%. This decline may reflect relative stability in the industry, with few new firms entering the market. Switzerland, known for its quality of life and interest in cultural activities, continues to be an attractive location for businesses in the sector. Turkey recorded an increase of 1,977 businesses, a growth of 7.17%. This increase may reflect an expanding sector, supported by increased demand for leisure and cultural activities. Istanbul, with its vibrant art scene, could be a driver of this growth. Bulgaria saw an increase of 302 companies, equal to 6.20%. This increase reflects stable growth in the sector. Sofia, the capital, is an emerging cultural center. Croatia recorded an increase of 292 companies, with growth of 8.51%. This data indicates modest but constant growth in the sector. Zagreb, the capital, is known for its lively cultural scene. Cyprus saw an increase of 162 companies, equivalent to 7.25%. This increase reflects stable growth in the sector. Nicosia, the capital, is a growing cultural center. Malta recorded an increase of 235 businesses, with growth of 11.87%. This data suggests a significant

expansion of the sector. Valletta, the capital, is known for its lively cultural scene. North Macedonia saw an increase of 10 companies, amounting to 1.31%. This increase reflects modest but steady growth in the sector. Skopje, the capital, is an emerging cultural center. Romania recorded an increase of 2,377 companies, with a growth of 9.57%. This data indicates a strong expansion of the sector. Bucharest, the capital, is a vibrant cultural center. Serbia saw an increase of 190 companies, equal to 10.05%. This increase reflects significant growth in the industry. Belgrade, the capital, is known for its vibrant cultural scene.

Economic Policies. Economic policies for business development in the arts, entertainment and recreation sector must be structured in such a way as to promote the sustainability and growth of this sector, recognizing its crucial role not only for the economy, but also for social cohesion and cultural well-being. First, it is crucial that governments offer targeted tax incentives to creative businesses, such as tax credits and tax breaks for investing in arts and cultural projects. This type of financial support can incentivize both new businesses to enter the market and existing businesses to expand their operations. Furthermore, access to financing must be facilitated through the creation of specific funds for arts and culture, managed at both national and regional level, to ensure that small businesses and creative start-ups can also access the capital needed to grow. In parallel, investment in cultural infrastructure is essential. This includes improving and maintaining theatres, museums, galleries and event spaces, as well as promoting new creative spaces such as artist coworking and shared workshops. Access to suitable, low-cost working spaces is crucial for artists and cultural businesses, especially in their early stages. Local governments can play a key role in this, offering unused public buildings on favorable terms or developing public-private partnerships for the management of such spaces. Training and education represent another fundamental pillar for the development of the sector. Policies should include significant investments in artistic and management training, both through schools and universities, and through continuing education programs and specific workshops for cultural entrepreneurs. It is important for artists and creatives to not only perfect their artistic skills, but also acquire practical management, financial and marketing knowledge to be able to effectively manage their businesses. Economic policies must also promote digitalisation and technological innovation in the arts and entertainment sector. This includes support for the development of digital platforms that can broaden access to works of art and cultural events, making it easier to reach wider audiences. The technology can also be used to improve user experiences, through augmented and virtual reality, or for the creation of new digital art forms. Incentives for technological innovation, such as funding for research and development projects or partnerships with universities and research centers, can stimulate growth in the sector. Another critical area is the promotion of cultural exports. Policies should include support for participation in international fairs, festivals and exhibitions, as well as cultural exchange programs that can help artists and creative businesses become known abroad. Trade missions and internationalization programs can be effective tools for opening new markets and creating opportunities for international collaboration. Furthermore, cultural diplomacy can play a strategic role in promoting national culture and building positive international relations. The role of public policies is also to encourage collaboration between different actors in the cultural and creative sector. Creating networks and clusters can facilitate the exchange of ideas and resources, promoting innovation and growth. Networking platforms, discussion forums and conferences can be useful for connecting artists, entrepreneurs, investors and institutional representatives. Policies should therefore support the creation of trade associations and other forms of collective organization that can represent the interests of the sector and foster cooperation. Finally, it is important that economic policies are inclusive and accessible to all segments of the population. This means ensuring that development opportunities in the arts and entertainment sector are open to people of all ages,

ethnicities and socio-economic backgrounds. Policies should promote diversity and inclusion, ensuring that minorities and disadvantaged communities have access to the same supports and opportunities. Specific programs to support women and young people in the creative sector can contribute to greater equity and an enrichment of the cultural landscape.

Conclusions. Between 2021 and 2022, the number of businesses operating in the arts, entertainment and recreation sector grew by an average of 2.24%. There are countries in which the value of the number of companies operating in the arts, entertainment and recreation sector grew significantly between 2021 and 2022 in Latvia with +22.23%, Estonia with +19.99% and Norway with +15.93%. There are countries in which the number of such companies decreased between 2021 and 2022, namely Luxembourg with -8.88%, Austria with -11.62% and Sweden with -11.74%.

Declarations

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